

Paper 10

A STUDY ON SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT LIFE CYCLE

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Srinivas University, Mangalore, Indiageminichaitra@gmail.com lesleeta.12@gmail.com**Abstract**

Computer is one of the major parts of our life, its used in various fields such as education, medicine, industry etc. Organizations are dependent on these computer technologies for their work, with the use of computer we can perform complicated task in short duration of time which saves time. The needs of organization vary accordingly, which has led to evolution of number of software development companies. These companies develop the software according to the complicated requirement of clients and also modifies the software according to their needs. Software Engineering is a systematic approach for development, operation and maintenance of software.

Software development life cycle is a structure imposed on developing high quality, reliable, cost effective and within time software products in the software industry. Which can also be called as software development model. Its an approach for the development of a reliable high-quality software system. There are different Software development life cycle models available such as Waterfall model, Iterative model, Spiral model, V model. Each describing the approach to variety of task or activities that takes place during the process. Each of the software development model has its own features. Quality of software is the major concern and software development life cycle minimizes the risk and failure of software product.

Keywords: Software Engineering, Software development life cycle, v model.**Different stages of software development life cycle:**

Software Development life cycle includes various phases outlining how the software project sould be developed, designed and maintained to ensure that all functional & user specifications, goals and objectives are achieved in various phases, the following phases are included:

- **Requirement Analysis**
- **Software Design**
- **Software Coding**
- **Software Testing and**
- **Maintenance.**

Requirement Analysis begins the life cycle of software development. And the cycle ends with Maintenance phase.

Requirement Analysis

All related data and customer requirements information were collected and analyzed in the requirement analysis. Specification of the software specification (SRS) is then established. Project plans are produced in SRS which identify the activities to be carried out during the project. The aim of this phase is to capture all the details of the project or we can imply that the requirement analysis phase is to capture the details of each requirement and to ensure that everyone understands the nature of the task and how each requirement is to be met.

Software Design

The high level design of the software and system will be addressed during the design phase in order to be able to fulfill each specification. The technical details of the project will be discussed with the stakeholders and various criteria will be checked and the best design strategy for the product is selected.

Software Coding

This is the phase where we actually implement all the requirements which are gathered from the client. In these phases coding is started as per the requirement of the client. Coding is translating the design structure into a programming language.

Software Testing

Testing is the final phase of the Software Development Life Cycle before clients receive the software. In this phase we check whether or not our software works as expected. We also test that SRS meets the complete software specification specified by the client at the time of the agreement. We ensure that the code is free of errors in this process.

Software maintenance

Software maintenance is required after checking the entire software. The software maintenance objective is to make the software functional according to client specifications and to provide service continuity. If a problem is found in the production process, the development team is told and depending on how serious the problem is, it may either involve a hotfix that is produced and delivered in a short time or, if not very serious, it may wait until the next version of the software.

Software development life cycle models

There are different Software development life cycle models available such as:

- **Waterfall model**
- **Iterative model**
- **Spiral model**
- **V model**

Waterfall model

Waterfall model is the software process model that is simplest and traditional. Most of the waterfall model is used for small projects. This model is working in a linear order. The linear order of this phase is as follows:

- Requirement analysis
- Software Design
- Software coding
- Software Testing and
- Maintenance

The output of one stage used in this design as the input to the next phase. So, it's also called a linear model of the sequence. Every stage is completed in this model before entering the next step. After moving to the next stage, there is no option to return. This model is very easy to understand and it's not very expensive. Nonetheless, this design is not useful when it comes to large projects and will only be discovered after system testing. The biggest disadvantages of this model are that the requirement is clear because no client intervention is permitted between the project. If a specification is therefore wrong or lacking, it will not become clear until the late stages of the life cycle.

V Model

V model is similar to Waterfall model, V model is divided into two parts. One part deals with the analysis of requirements and the other part deals with the test activities. In this model, each phase has the testing activities as opposed to the waterfall model where testing activities are carried out after completion of the project, this model helps to improve the software development.

Here we can't move to the next stage until the previous one is done and because of checking a activity after each phase this allows us to meet the actual project target. But it requires more time due to testing activity after each phase.

Iterative Model

The design can be built in small chunks with the Iterative method, each modified chunk includes some additional features. With each iteration some new requirements are introduced and the software is modified and this process continues until the complete design is not completed. The software is developed here in a looping form.

Different stages of these models are as follows:

- **Requirement**
- **Design**
- **Implementation and**
- **Evaluation**

Next set of requirements will be observed during the evaluation phase.

Spiral Model

As the name implies it has many cycles which is spiral shaped. Each cycle is divided into 4 sections:

- **Planning:** In this section the objective of the software is been determined. And even the alternative is identified
- **Risk analysis:** Here analysisation of risk is done and risk is resolved.
- **Development:** As the name implies here the software is been developed and next level product verification is done.
- **Client Evaluation:** Here the client is allowed to evaluate the product that has been developed.

And these four steps are repeated unit the software is completely developed. That is in progressive way, it has phases similar to Waterfall model. Spiral model is best suited for the highly personalized and large software product because in this model user interaction and evaluation is started from the early stage of the development. But this model not for small projects. And this model is even time consuming.

Conclusion:

There are different model of Software development based on the needs and criteria appropriate software development model is been selected. Each model used for software development has its own advantages and disadvantage. The development of software must be done on time if not any delay in the development of final product may lead to a situation where the market doesn't want this product anymore which is developed as it may become obsolete in the market due to the competition which is very high in the market. As there are lots of company which are into software development meeting the client requirement at right time is really important.

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